

The Indus Valley Civilization

by **Mamoni Das**, *Department of History,
Indira Gandhi National Open University,
Maidan Garhi, New Delhi - 110068, India*

Email: mamonidaspb@gmail.com

Abstract :

The more noteworthy Indus region was home to the biggest of the four old urban civilization establishments of Egypt, Mesopotamia, South Asia and China. It was not found until the 1920's. A large portion of its vestiges, even its significant urban areas, stay to be uncovered. The old Indus Civilization script has not been deciphered. Many inquiries concerning the Indus individuals who made this profoundly complex culture stay unanswered, however different parts of their general public can be replied through different sorts of archeological investigations. Harappa was a city in the Indus human advancement that thrived around 2600 to 1700 B.C.E. in the western piece of South Asia.

Keywords: Indus valley civilization.

Introduction :

In some cases, disclosures of great cultures of the past have been made unintentionally. In 1856, Brothers James and William Burton who were occupied with laying out the railroad line from Karachi to Lahore attempted to get blocks for their line from the close-by hills. This burrowing prompted the revelation of two antiquated urban communities, Harappa in West Punjab and Mohenjo-Daro in Sind.

The credit of inquiry of this obscure human progress goes conveyed to Ray Bahadur Dayaram. He uncovered this place in 1921 under the direction of Sir John Marshall. After roughly, 1 year in 1922 at the season of uncovering one more place was found in Larkana at Pakistan. Keeping in view the information of this place it was accepted that this human advancement was restricted just to Sindhu Valley. Thus, this human advancement was called by the name 'Sindhu valley'. The urban culture of the Bronze Age found in Harappa in Pakistani. Punjab was a way softening revelation Up 1853, A. Cunningham, the British designer who turned into an extraordinary excavator voyager, saw a Harappan seal. Then the seal demonstrated a bull and six composed letters, he didn't understand its significance much later, in 1921, the possibility of the site of Harappa was acknowledged when an Indian classicist, Daya Ram Sahni, began exhuming it. At about a similar time, R.D. Banerjee, a history specialist, unearthed the site of Mohenjo-Daro in Sindh.

In the post-Independence period, archeologists from both India and Pakistan uncovered the Harappan and associated destinations. Suraj Bhan, M.K. Dhavalikar, J.P. Joshi, B.B. Lal, S.R. Rao, B.K. Thapar, R.S. Bisht, and others worked in Gujarat, Haryana, and Rajasthan. In Pakistan, Kot Diji in the focal Indus Valley was exhumed by E.A. Khan and incredible considerations were paid to the Hakra and pre-Hakra societies by M.R. Mughal. An H. Dani unearthed the Gandhara the graves in the North-West Frontier Province of Pakistan. American, British, French, and Italian archeologists additionally worked at a few locales including Harappa.

Date of Civilization:

The Indus Valley Civilization grew and developed at the same time when other civilization in other parts of Africa and Asia, mainly in the Valleys of the rivers the Nile, the Euphrates, the Tigris and the Hwang-Ho. The Harappan Culture became important about 4,500 years ago, or as people normally says, in about 2,500 B.C. (Before Christ).

Society:

The Terracotta figure gives us the best information about the social life of the people. Probably Merchant classes were ruling the Indus Valley Civilization. The weapons such as axes, bows, arrows, and gada were used. No defense weapons

swords were discovered. The Indus Valley Civilization has a population of over 5 million people (Approximately). The Indus Valley people consisted of Australoids, Mediterranean, Mongoloid and Alpine races.

Religion:

The Indus people did not have an organized religious system, as they did not construct temples. They worship gods in the form of tree (Pipal) and animals (unicorn). They also believe in ghosts and evil forces and used amulets as protection against them. The chief male deity was the Pashupati Mahadeva, represented in seals and chief female deity was the Mother Goddess, depicted in various forms. There is also a sufficient evidence of phallic worship. Besides those of phallus, numerous stone symbols of female sex organs (yoni, worship) were discovered. The worship of fire is proved by the discovery of fire alters at Lothal, Kalibangan, and Harappa.

Weights:

The urban population of the Indus people required more, utilized weights and measures for trade and different exchanges. Various articles utilized for weights have been found. They demonstrate that in weighing for the most part 16 or its multiples were utilized. For example 16, 64, 160, 320 and 640. Curiously the convention of 16 has proceeded in India till present day times and till as of late 16 annas made one Rs. The Harappans additionally knew the craft of estimation. We have run over sticks engraved with measure marks one of these is made by bronze.

Economy:

The people ate wheat and barley, which they ground in millstones and then baked into bread. They liked fruit, such as pomegranates and bananas. The staple food of the people comprised wheat, barley, rice, milk and some vegetables like peas, sesamum, and fruits like date palms. Mutton, pork, poultry, fish, etc. were also eaten by the Indus people.

Clothes:

Many spindles were discovered at the Harappan sites. This proves the use of cotton for weaving social cloths. Probably wool was also used. The garments might

have been sewn. The women wore a short skirt which was held at the waist by a girdle. The men wrapped long pieces of cloth around themselves.

Agriculture:

By and by the rainless, Indus district is not prolific. However, its prosperous towns and towns in the past demonstrate that it was ripe in old circumstances. At the exhibit, it has just a rainfall of around 15 cm. In the fourth century B.C., one of the antiquarians of Alexander composes that Sindh was a rich piece of the nation. In prior circumstances, the Indus area had more characteristic vegetation which Pulled in more rains. It provided timber fuel for preparing blocks on a substantial scale and furthermore for development. With the section of time, common vegetation was annihilated by the expansion of farming, huge scale touching, and supply of fuel. A significantly more essential explanation behind the ripeness of the zone appears to have been the yearly immersion in the Indus stream. The Indus individuals sowed seeds in the surge fields in November when the surge water subsided and procured their harvests of wheat and Barley in April before the coming of the following surge. The Harappans most likely utilized the wooden plowshare. We do not know whether the furrow was drawn by men or bulls. The Harappan people produced wheat, barley, rai, peas. Wheat and barley were grown in large quantity, as large quantity of barley was found at Banawali.

Trade:

The Indus people have a trading relationship with the people of Sumer and towns lying along the Persian Gulf. The sent goods from one place to another, as objects and seals made in Mohenjo-Daro have been found in Iraq. The trade was carried by ships from Lothal (where a dock has been found) and incoming goods were also received here.

Following are the commodities which were imported by Harappa citizens:

- Afghanistan - Tin, Silver, Gold, Led Himalaya - Mineral pitch.
- Iran - Tin, Silver, Led Khetadi - Copper.
- Baluchistan - Copper, Stealite South India - Gold, Shell, Grey.
- Faras - Gold Rajasthan - Stealite, Led.

- Mesopotamia - Lapis, Lazuli Gujarat - Stealite.
- Badaksha - Blue Diamond. Maharastra - Sapphire.
- Saurashtra - Shell, Grey.
- Neelgiri - Green Stone.

Following are the commodities which were exported by Harappa citizens:

- Faras (bay): Gold, Silver, Copper, Lapis Lazuli, bead of stone, ivory comb, Soot, Many types of Wooden, Diamond, Monkeys, Peacock.
- Sumar: Marbal seals, Diamond, Images Wooden.
- Greek: Cotton.
- Babylon: Cotton.
- Mesopotamia: Diamonds.
- Egypt: Diamonds, Neckless, Stool, Images, Candle stand, spoons.

Seals:

Seals were made of clay or stone. The seals had a design on one side; usually, the picture of a bull, a tree or some scene and above the picture was a line of pictographs (picture like sign used as a script by Harappan). These seals were perhaps used by merchants and traders to stamp their goods.

The fall of the Harappa's:

The Harappan culture lasted for about a thousand years. By 1500 B.C., when the Aryans began to arrive in India, the Harappan culture had collapsed. Why did this happen? The cities may have been destroyed by massive floods in the Indus must have been a potent cause for the extinction of the Harappan culture. The point is proved by the silt-clay that covers the collapsed houses at Mohenjo-Daro. Repeated floods must have forced the people to flee the inundated places and set up permanent habitat elsewhere. Or by an epidemic or some terrible disease when an epidemic like plague visits a human habitation, it leaves its trail of death everywhere. The scattered skeletal remains, therefore, lead some to attribute it to epidemic like plague, though there is no concrete proof of outbreak of plague in the region. The climate also began to change and the region became more and drier like a desert. Or else the cities might

have been attacked and the inhabitants were unable to defend themselves. The decline of the Harappan cities was a negative step in the history of India. The Aryans who came afterward knew nothing of city life. It took nearly another thousand years to boost cities again in India.

Facts about Indus Valley Civilization:

- The first mention of possibility of the Harappan Civilization was made early as 1826, by Charles Masen.
- The Civilization was named “Indus Valley Civilization” by Sir John Marshal (1924) after its discovery by Daga Ram Shana and Vatsa in 1921-22.
- A maximum number of sites were explored by S.R. Rao in Gujarat (1990).
- Around 2600 sites have been found in which 350 have been excavated.
- The Mohenjo Daro is the largest in Indus Valley Civilization. Aladdin is the smallest.
- Dholavira and the Rakhigarhi are the largest sites in India.

Conclusion:

The Indus Valley people gave to the world its earliest cities, its town planning, its architecture in stone and clay, and showed their concern for health and sanitation. They built a scientific drainage system in their cities. Indus Valley civilization is renowned for its vast agrarian growth and advancement; it was a forerunner of well structured constructions. The civilization also birthed a codified written language for accounting activities spurred by the numerous economic activities which took place in the hub of the cities garnering so much growth, urbane life styles and development. The level of intelligence and creativity elaborated by the inhabitants of the Indus Valley is astounding, that the civilization sprouts up autonomously remains highly debatable with skeptics suggesting that the civilization borrowed heavily from Mesopotamia.

References:

1. “Archeological Site of Harappa”. World Heritage Centre. UNESCO. Retrieved 19 February, 2013.

2. Aronovsky, Leona; Goliaths, Sutra (2005): *The Indus Valley*. Chicago: Heinemann.
3. Basham, A.L. (1968): Review of *A Short History of Pakistan* by A.H. Dani, Karachi: University of Karachi Press.
4. Kenoyer, J.M. (1997): *Trade and Technology of the Indus Valley: New insights from Harappa Pakistan*, World Archaeology.
5. Lal, B.B. (1997): *The Earliest Civilization of South Asia (Rise, Maturity and Decline)*.
6. Pittman, Holly (1984): *Art of the Bronze Age: Southeastern Iran, Western Central Asia, and the Indus Valley*, New York.
7. Possehl, G.L. (2002): *The Indus Civilization: A Contemporary Perspective*, Vistaar Publication, New Delhi.
8. 2007. Harappan Weights. *Puratattva* 37: 213-217.